

Biomass-derived activated carbons for the reclamation of fluorinated gases

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Fluorinated gases (F-gases) are a family of synthetic gases used in a large range of industrial applications, being used as substitutes for ozone-depleting substances. F-gases are powerful greenhouse gases (GHG) with global warming effects up to 23 000 times greater than carbon dioxide.^[1] In the EU, their emissions have increased up to 60% since 1990 in contrast to all other greenhouse gases whose emissions have been reduced. The development of technologies for efficient reclamation of F-gases is relevant, not only to reduce GHG emissions to the atmosphere, but also because their market value. Activated carbons (ACs) obtained from residual biomass have become attractive because they add economic value to cheap raw materials. Maize is the most produced cereal in the world and maize cob waste is a lignocellulosic material that can be considered a suitable raw material to obtain ACs with good adsorption properties.^[2]

This work aims to reduce the environmental impact of the most used F-gases in air conditioning, commercial refrigeration, electrical circuit industry, thermal insulators, and electronic semiconductors, such as, difluoromethane (R-32), 1,1,1,2-tetrafluoromethane (R-134a), pentafluoroethane (R-125) and sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆). The development of biomass-derived ACs with distinct porosity characteristics and subjected to different basic/acid treatments allows to fine-tune the specific interactions between the surface of the materials and the F-gases and thus selectivity. These materials have been evaluated by measuring the equilibrium^[3,4] and kinetics^[5] of adsorption of the pure gases and mixtures. Also, breakthrough experiments were performed to study the dynamic behaviour, validate a mathematical model for process design by simulation, and develop novel adsorption processes,^[5] using the biomass-derived ACs for reclamation of the most commonly used F-gases, which is a promising and attractive solution, providing commercial value to existing biomass waste.

References

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